

MODERNIZATION OF THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF ENTERPRISES OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF OWNERSHIP

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8363175>

Abstract: This article provides information about the modernization of the management system of various ownership enterprises and the constant striving of the enterprise for efficient production, decentralization of management, specialization of production and its diversification, and improvement of the economic mechanism.

Key words: economic mechanism, diversification, decentralization, management decentralization, production, modernization, management system.

Inevitable competition in the conditions of the market economy requires enterprises to modernize all aspects of economic activity, in particular, the management system. In this regard, based on the experience of highly developed countries and advanced local enterprises, the following can be indicated as the main directions of modernization of the management system.

1. Based on the experience of developed countries in the conditions of management decentralization, that is, doing business and entrepreneurship, it can be said that the adaptation of the enterprise to today's rapid changes depends on the centralized (or decentralized) level of the management system. It mainly depends on the degree to which the authority of the upper level moves to the lower levels of management or remains at the same level.

The effective operation of a multi-level structure requires the development of extended rules and guidelines. As a result, they reduce the management structure's ability to operationally influence changing conditions. Therefore, since the 70s, in the conditions of rapidly changing demand, rapid end of life cycles of many goods, expansion of product nomenclature, reduction of production volume, complexity of technological processes, increasing demand for the quality of goods and services, management decentralization has become of primary importance. is falling Because on the one hand, it gives an opportunity to quickly influence the demands of consumers, on the other hand, it speeds up the decision-making process. Decentralization of management is carried out in two interrelated directions, i.e., in decision-making, the distribution of authority, or in large companies, a relatively small autonomous body that has the right to make decisions on economic and production issues. occurs by simplifying the management structure by moving to structural units.

There are a number of reasons why the powers of senior managers are distributed to lower managers. There are many uncertainties and risks in production and economic activities, the main features of the enterprise's development are gradually changing, and the implementation of production processes is becoming more complicated. Therefore, no leader has the ability to fully control all the changes and processes taking place. This problem can be solved by distributing the powers of the upper level to the lower levels. In this case, it should be remembered that in the distribution of powers, the obligations of leaders are not reduced,

on the contrary, they remain responsible for their actions and those of their subordinates, but the opportunities of leaders are expanded.

2. Specialization of production and its diversification. It is known that specialization serves as the basis for the enterprise to take the leading position in the market. Also, it is necessary to engage in diversification while getting the maximum benefit from specialization. Specialization and diversification may not bring high profits for the company separately. Therefore, the task of management includes the correct establishment and organization of the mutual ratio between them, because it is this ratio that determines the economy of resources, the stability of the enterprise and economic growth. Here, such a formula should be used, in which $2X2$ should be less than 5.[2]

3. Improvement of economic mechanism. Management organizational structure, motivation and management methods should be used in such a way that it is understood not only to adapt the enterprise to the changes occurring in the environment, but also to create an opportunity to be ready for tomorrow's changes. According to the experience of prestigious companies of industrially developed countries, new approaches to business and a number of innovations are based on the improvement of management. For example, we can cite the approach of creating one's own buyer. Its main goal is to create a product that motivates the buyer to change his needs, and in this case only knowledge and experience can ensure the future of the company's product.

4. The enterprise's constant pursuit of efficient production. There are three different ways of development of this direction. The first is based on the use of the "ideal business" model. Its content is that the established theoretical optimum of economic activity serves as a standard of real results. For example, General Motors chose this path when A.P. Sloan arrived in 1921, when he was on the verge of collapse, and became one of the great automobile companies in the future. A.P. Sloan started by considering what the company should look like in the American market, then he made a future work project, within 5 years the company was able to develop and reach the highest position in the market.

The second way is "maximum use of opportunities", that is, analyzing the company's activities in the past and present, and preparing for future changes. In this regard, the management should focus on determining the areas of activity that need to be developed as soon as possible and those that are not. At the same time, the enterprise will have to try to introduce innovations that allow to increase the results of its activity in the market.

The third is the effective use of resources by identifying the advantages that allow to achieve the highest results from the external activities of the enterprise.

The effective operation of the enterprise mainly depends on the correct identification of business opportunities. It is known that the stability and economic growth of the enterprise depends on the constant identification and proper use of its capabilities, and it should be assumed that no matter how efficiently the enterprise operates, its actual results will still be lower than the theoretical optimal results. Because business opportunities are always higher than actual activities.

5. Achieving stability in enterprise activity. An enterprise can achieve sustainability in different ways. First, this is done by strengthening their relationships with their customers. This should be based on the principle that if the company does not provide high-quality

service to its customers, it will always fail. In practice, customers are carefully studied and analyzed in order to study the demand.

Secondly, the company should know its competitors well. In this case, the management system will have to direct the marketing activities to carry out a strong marketing policy, and based on this, who are the competitors of the company, what is helping them to attract and retain their customers, and how to keep these customers. It is necessary to know the exact answer to the questions of what to do to turn it to the side.[3]

One of the next important factors in ensuring the stability of the enterprise is the constant adaptation of management to changes in the external environment (ie, quality, economy, technology, etc.). But the company should have a clear understanding of each change while adapting to any change. This can be achieved, on the one hand, by developing an enterprise development strategy, and on the other hand, by using strategic planning together with long-term and short-term planning.

Today, in the period of development of science and technology, the enterprise is always under the influence of fierce competition. Therefore, in order to maintain its stability, the enterprise must have a reserve of strength.

Production and financial resources of any enterprise are usually limited. Therefore, the economic entity needs to effectively use the available personnel and equipment. This is achieved with the help of the product sales and production management organization system. Today, the main attention is paid to the quality of the product due to the increasing competition to take its place in the market. This factor, in turn, requires changes in the product quality management system. Management of quality control of products produced in foreign countries is reflected in the system of creating conditions for the production of high-quality products and focuses on general control at all stages of the production process. In this regard, the experience of Japanese companies is noteworthy. Its content is that if the percentage of defects of any product exceeds 0.001% in the search for probability, this product is excluded from production as being of poor quality. It is this number that determines the level of the defect.

6. Constantly striving for the future in improving the management system and separate system units. If this direction is not applied, the management of the enterprise will remain dependent on the current situation in the external environment. However, this direction can be effectively implemented only if the following questions are constantly researched:

- how to get better results?
- what is stopping us?
- what is the company doing well, and what is it doing poorly?

The management system should always strive to find the knowledge that is relevant to the consumer from the point of view of value and satisfaction.

In this case, knowledge is understood as the ability to use information to perform a specific task. In business, knowledge itself is considered useless if it is not used for some purpose.[1]

We believe that as a result of the implementation of the above considerations by industrial enterprises operating in various forms of ownership, wide opportunities will be created for their rapid development.

Conclusion:

For example, the laws issued on the modernization of the management system of various proprietary enterprises and the constant striving of the enterprise for efficient production, decentralization of management, specialization of production and its diversification, production of ways to improve the economic mechanism and the development and modernization of the ways of their implementation we can see.

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